

Adsorptive degradation of blister agent simulant by zeolite NaA/WO₃/NiFe₂O₄ nanocomposite adsorbent from water media

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Abstract.

In this research, we report the fabrication of the novel zeolite NaA/WO₃/NiFe₂O₄ nanocomposite adsorbent by ultrasound-assisted hydrothermal method for the adsorptive degradation of chloroethyl ethyl sulfide (CEES), a simulant of blister agent. The fabricated NaA/WO₃/NiFe₂O₄ nanocomposite was identified via FESEM, EDAX, XRD, FTIR, BET, and VSM. The degradation kinetics of CEES was studied on the NaA/WO₃/NiFe₂O₄ nanocomposite by GC-FID analysis and it was concluded that this nanocomposite gives efficient removal features against CEES. Lastly, the reaction products namely hydroxyethyl ethyl sulfide (HEES) and ethyl vinyl sulfide (EVS) were distinguished using GC-MS analysis.

Keywords: zeolite NaA/WO₃/NiFe₂O₄, chloroethyl ethyl sulfide (CEES), adsorptive degradation, hydroxyethyl ethyl sulfide (HEES), ethyl vinyl sulfide (EVS).